

THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN IRONY AND SARCASM THROUGH LITERATURE WORKS

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Abstract: In this study, we will discuss the difference between irony and sarcasm and understanding the difference between irony and sarcasm is of utmost importance in the study of literature. Irony refers to a situation or statement that is contrary to what is expected or intended, often resulting in humor or a deeper meaning. Sarcasm, on the other hand, is a form of verbal irony that involves saying the opposite of what one means with the intention to mock or ridicule. By distinguishing between these two literary devices, readers can fully appreciate the nuanced messages conveyed by authors in their works.

Key words: irony, sarcasm, literature, literary devices, authors

Irony and sarcasm are two literary devices often used interchangeably, but they have distinct differences. Irony is characterized by the use of words to convey a meaning that is opposite to its literal meaning, while sarcasm is a form of irony that takes a mocking or contemptuous tone. Both techniques are frequently employed in literature to enhance the meaning and impact of a text. By examining various works of literature, it is possible to gain a deeper understanding of the nuances between irony and sarcasm.

Irony refers to the use of words or situations that convey a meaning opposite to their literal or expected meaning. It is a rhetorical device used to create humor, emphasize contrasts, or express criticism. Irony can be classified into three types: verbal irony, situational irony, and dramatic irony. Verbal irony occurs when someone says something but means the opposite. Situational irony happens when there is a discrepancy between what is expected to happen and what actually happens. Dramatic irony occurs when the audience knows something that the characters in a story do not. Understanding irony requires careful analysis and interpretation of context and language.

Sarcasm is a form of irony that involves using language to express the opposite of what is actually meant, often for humorous or mocking effect. It is often characterized by a mocking or scornful tone and is intended to convey contempt or ridicule towards a person, situation, or idea. Sarcasm can be found in various forms of literature, such as plays, novels, and poetry, where it is used to critique social norms or expose hypocrisy. Understanding sarcasm requires recognizing the disparity between the literal meaning of the words and the intended meaning conveyed through tone and context.

Irony is a literary device that involves a contradiction between what is expected and what actually occurs. It adds depth and complexity to literature by challenging the reader's understanding of the text. Irony can be found in various forms, such as situational irony, verbal irony, and dramatic irony. It is often used to convey a message or to create humor. Irony can be seen in works such as Jane Austen's *Pride and Prejudice*, where the seemingly perfect relationship between Elizabeth Bennet and Mr. Darcy is filled with misunderstandings and mistaken judgments¹.

One example of irony in literature is found in Mark Twain's *The Adventures of Huckleberry Finn*. Throughout the novel, Huck Finn struggles with the morality of slavery, yet he continues to participate in it by helping Jim, a runaway slave. This irony highlights the hypocrisy and contradictions in the society depicted in the novel. Another example can be seen in William Shakespeare's play *Romeo and Juliet*, where the audience knows that Juliet is not actually dead, but Romeo does not, leading to tragic consequences. This dramatic irony adds depth and suspense to the story².

Situational irony occurs when the outcome of a situation is contrary to what was expected. It involves a discrepancy between what is expected to happen and what actually happens. For example, in Nathaniel Hawthorne's "*The Scarlet Letter*", Reverend Dimmesdale is viewed by the townspeople as a paragon of virtue and righteousness, yet he is secretly the father of Hester Prynne's child,

¹ Austen, Jane. *Pride and Prejudice*. London: Printed for T. Egerton, 1813.

² Twain, Mark. *Adventures of Huckleberry Finn*. Chatto & Windus, London, 1884.

Pearl. This situational irony creates tension and suspense in the narrative as the reader anticipates the revelation of Dimmesdale's guilt.

Verbal irony is a figure of speech that occurs when someone says something that is deliberately different from what they actually mean. It involves using words to convey a meaning that is the opposite of their literal meaning, often to create humor or emphasize a point. Examples of verbal irony can be found in various forms of literature, such as plays, novels, and poems. For instance, in William Shakespeare's play *Romeo and Juliet*, Juliet exclaims "O Romeo, Romeo! Wherefore art thou Romeo?" while knowing that Romeo is listening but hidden from her view. This statement is ironic because Juliet is not actually wondering where Romeo is, but rather why he is a member of the enemy family, the Montagues, further emphasizing the point that their love is forbidden.

Dramatic irony is a literary device used to create tension and engage the audience by allowing them to possess knowledge that the characters do not. It occurs when the audience is aware of information that contradicts the beliefs or expectations of the characters, leading to misunderstanding or misreading of the situation. This technique is often used to create suspense and build anticipation in works of literature. For example, in Shakespeare's play *Romeo and Juliet*, the audience knows that Juliet is not actually dead, but Romeo, believing she is, tragically takes his own life.

Sarcasm is a literary device often used to convey irony or mockery in literature. It serves as a means of expressing a humorous or critical tone through the use of ironic remarks or statements. For example, in Jane Austen's novel *Pride and Prejudice*, the character Mr. Bennet frequently employs sarcasm to satirize the societal norms and conventions of his time. Through his sarcastic remarks, Austen effectively critiques the absurdities and hypocrisies prevalent in Regency society. Moreover, sarcasm adds depth and complexity to the characters and their interactions, providing a nuanced commentary on social dynamics and human nature in literature.

Sarcasm is a literary technique that is widely used to express irony and make critical or mocking remarks. In literature works, sarcasm can be found in various forms, such as in dialogue, character descriptions, and narrative passages. For example, in Mark Twain's "*The Adventures of Huckleberry Finn*," the character of Pap Finn is portrayed as an ignorant and racist individual whose derogatory remarks about African Americans are laced with sarcasm. This serves to highlight the hypocrisy and ignorance of such attitudes in society. (Other

examples can be found in Jonathan Swift's "A Modest Proposal," where the entire essay is a sarcastic commentary on the dehumanization of the poor³.

1) Use of sarcasm in dialogue

The use of sarcasm in dialogue is a literary technique that adds depth and complexity to a character's words and actions. Sarcasm is often employed to convey irony and satire, highlighting the disparity between what is said and what is meant. Through the use of sarcasm, authors can create layers of meaning and evoke a range of emotions in readers. For example, in Mark Twain's novel *Adventures of Huckleberry Finn*, the character of Huck frequently uses sarcasm to criticize societal norms and expose the hypocrisy of the time. Sarcasm in dialogue is an effective tool for writers to engage readers and convey nuanced messages⁴.

2) Sarcasm as a form of social commentary

Sarcasm, a form of verbal irony, is often used as a means of social commentary. Through the use of biting, mocking language, sarcasm allows individuals to express disapproval or criticism in a humorous and indirect way. By employing sarcasm, individuals can address sensitive or controversial topics without directly attacking them. For example, in Mark Twain's novel *The Adventures of Huckleberry Finn*, the character of Huck frequently uses sarcasm to highlight the absurdity and hypocrisy of societal norms. Sarcasm serves as a powerful tool for social commentary, providing a means of critique while also entertaining the audience.

Irony and sarcasm are often used interchangeably, but they have distinct characteristics. Irony involves an expression of meaning that is the opposite of the literal interpretation of the words used, often used to convey humor or the unexpected. Sarcasm, on the other hand, involves the use of irony in a mocking or contemptuous manner, using tone and context to convey the intended meaning. While irony can be unintentional, sarcasm is always deliberate, aiming to criticize or ridicule. Understanding the differences between irony and sarcasm is crucial for interpreting literary works accurately.

Intention. Intention plays a crucial role in the use of irony and sarcasm in literature. Irony is characterized by a deliberate difference between what is expected and what actually occurs, often used to convey a deeper meaning or criticism⁵. On the other hand, sarcasm involves using irony to mock or ridicule

³ Jonathan Swift. *A Modest Proposal: The Original 1729 Edition*

⁴ Twain, Mark. *Adventures of Huckleberry Finn*. Chatto & Windus, London, 1884.

⁵ Wayne C. Booth. *A Rhetoric of Irony*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1974.

someone or something, often with a negative or bitter tone⁶. The intention behind the use of irony or sarcasm can vary depending on the author's purpose and desired effect on the reader.

Tone. Tone refers to the attitude or mood conveyed by a writer or speaker in a text. It can be conveyed through word choice, sentence structure, and overall style. In literature, tone plays a crucial role in shaping the reader's perception of the text and its underlying messages. For example, in Mark Twain's "The Adventures of Huckleberry Finn," the tone is often satirical and mocking, highlighting the flaws and hypocrisy in society. Similarly, in Jonathan Swift's "A Modest Proposal," the tone is ironic, using exaggerated and outrageous statements to criticize the indifference towards poverty.

Audience perception. Audience perception plays a crucial role in understanding the difference between irony and sarcasm in literature works. Irony relies on the audience's ability to recognize the discrepancy between what is said and what is meant, while sarcasm relies on the audience's ability to detect the speaker's mocking or contemptuous tone. The effectiveness of irony and sarcasm is contingent upon the audience's knowledge, experience, and cultural background, as these factors contribute to their interpretation of the author's intent.

One example of a literature work that employs both irony and sarcasm is Jonathan Swift's "A Modest Proposal." In this satirical essay, Swift suggests that the impoverished Irish people should sell their children as food to solve the problem of famine. The use of irony is evident in the outrageous proposal, which ultimately criticizes the indifference and inaction of the upper classes towards the suffering of the poor. Sarcasm is employed through Swift's tone of mock sincerity as he presents his horrific solution with seemingly logical arguments.

References:

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⁶ Salvatore Attardo. *Linguistic Theories of Humor*. In the series *Humor Research* 1. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter. 1994